

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from three ships - BC01, BC03 & BC10, from Barcode, Oslo.

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Samples from three ships found during excavations at Barcode in Oslo were submitted for dendrochronological analysis. A total of 17 boats were found and excavated at Barcode in Oslo over the past several years, and these are currently the subject of ongoing dendrochronological analysis (for example Daly 2010a&b, 2011d). Most of the Barcode boats are dating to the second half of the 16th century, but with one exception – BC17 is earlier (Daly 2013c&e).

All samples described in this report are of *Quercus sp.*, oak. There are seven samples from ship BC01, five from BC03 and two from BC10.

In the interest of open access to data and to enable researchers to utilise this material in the future, the measurements are printed in the catalogue. All measurements will also be submitted to the Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology (DCCD, www.dendrochronology.eu). For measuring and for the analysis and the calculation of the t-value ("t-test"), "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are employed.

Fig. 1. Dating diagram for Barcode ships BC01, BC03 & BC10, Oslo.

BC01

Of the seven samples from Barcode ship BC01, four have sapwood preserved. All samples are dated (see fig. 1). The tree-ring curves from three samples are so

similar to each other, they might come from the same tree. These three are averaged together to form a single tree-ring curve representing that tree. The felling date for the trees used to make ship BC01 is estimated, by allowing for missing sapwood. If we assume that all trees were felled at the same time, this felling took place in the period c. **AD 1598-1604** (marked in green in fig. 1). The oaks used to build BC01 grew in Southern Norway so a sapwood statistic for Norway is used. Oaks here have, on average, 15 (-8 +6) sapwood years (Christensen & Havemann 1998).

One of the samples is labelled “reparationsbord” repair plank (x160). This sample has only heartwood preserved, and allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that the sample comes from is estimated to after c. AD 1590. The high correlation between this sample and the samples from the ship’s primary phase indicate that the repair timber grew in the same region as the original ship’s timbers. Dendrochronologically, this timber could easily belong to the primary phase, both in terms of its similarity to the primary timbers and in terms of the dating result.

BC03

Of the five oak samples from BC03 two have sapwood preserved. All five samples are dated (fig. 1). Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the trees that were used to make the boat are estimated to have taken place c. **AD 1605-18** (marked in blue in fig. 1). As the trees used to build this boat come from Southern Norway (see below), the sapwood estimate for Norway is again used.

			Z111002a	Z111001a	Z110004a	Z110001a	Z110005a	Z110003a	Z110002a	Z1090049	Z109007a	Z109001a	Z1090029	Z1090059	Z109003a	Z109006a
BC10	Z111002a	*	-	\	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Z111001a	-	*	\	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,08	-	-	-	-
	Z110004a	\	\	*	-	-	-	-	\	\		4	5,44	\	-	-
Z110M001	BC03	Z110001a	-	-	-	*	7,38	4,76	3,68	-	3,08	-	5,03	5,01	4,18	-
		Z110005a	-	-	-	7,38	*	9,54	4,97	5,36	3,84	4,85	6,2	5,79	4,02	-
		Z110003a	-	-	-	4,76	9,54	*	7,14	4,36	3,57	5,32	6,16	5,21	4,35	-
		Z110002a	-	-	-	3,68	4,97	7,14	*	4,83	4,03	4,42	3,7	-	3,44	-
Z109M001	BC01	Z1090049	-	-	\	-	5,36	4,36	4,83	*	7,27	5,74	5,57	6,51	5,25	-
		Z109007a	-	-	\	3,08	3,84	3,57	4,03	7,27	*	5,3	5,66	5,34	3,72	-
		Z109001a	-	3,08	4	-	4,85	5,32	4,42	5,74	5,3	*	12,79	12,19	4,07	-
		Z1090029	-	-	5,44	5,03	6,2	6,16	3,7	5,57	5,66	12,79	*	14,73	5,64	3,12
		Z1090059	-	-	\	5,01	5,79	5,21	-	6,51	5,34	12,19	14,73	*	4,45	3,49
		Z109003a	-	-	-	4,18	4,02	4,35	3,44	5,25	3,72	4,07	5,64	4,45	*	-
		Z109006a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,12	3,49	-	*

Table 1. Barcode ships BC01, BC03 & BC10, Oslo. Result of the internal correlation. The grey tone highlights the high t-values. The three highlighted in pink match so well together, that they might come from a single tree.

BC10

Just two samples are from ship BC10 and one of these has sapwood preserved. Both samples are dated. Sample x005, with sapwood preserved, is from a plank

made from a tree that grew in Southern Scandinavia. Allowing for missing sapwood, the tree that his plank was made from was felled in the period c. **AD 1550-64**. This analysis shows that the second plank is from a tree from a quite different source - the Southern Baltic region. A sapwood statistic for Poland is therefore used. Here oak trees have an average of 15 sapwood years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990). The tree for the second plank was felled after c. AD 1543.

Filenames	-	-	BC01 Z109 M001	BC03 Z110 M001	BC10 Z111001a	BC10 Z111002a	
-	Start	dates	AD1437	AD1342	AD1357	AD1387	
-	dates	end	AD1597	AD1601	AD1547	AD1533	
Master chronologies							
0M040005	AD1257	AD1615	-	-	-	5,19	Baltic 2 (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	5,13	5,65	4,65	-	Sjælland Denmark (Daly unpubl.)
PM670108	AD725	AD1985	5,08	-	-	-	Gdansk (Wazny pers comm.)
SM000012	AD1125	AD1720	4,30	5,90	3,52	-	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
SM000005	AD1274	AD1974	3,62	5,68	-	-	Skaane Blekinge (Bartholin pers comm)
81M00004	AD1350	AD1480	-	6,74	3,76	-	kirker i Vendsyssel W Sweden group (Daly 1998c)
Site chronologies (dominated by imported timber)							
4077M00Z	AD1310	AD1546	8,79	7,57	4,29	-	Nyborg Slot renaissance phase (Daly 2007a)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	6,44	6,32	4,61	-	Ålborg østerå + boulevarden (Daly 2000a, 2001)
2101M001	AD1487	AD1743	6,34	-	-	-	CPH B&W-grund (Daly 1997a&b)
stirling la...	AD1355	AD1592	6,06	5,99	6,28	-	Stirling Castle Scotland (Crone pers comm.)
CD60IZ01	AD1450	AD1635	6,01	-	3,77	-	Ryomgård (National Museum of Denmark, revised Daly 2007a)
EDINCAS2	AD1358	AD1509	5,50	5,79	-	-	Edinburgh Castle (Crone pers comm.)
0691006S	AD1375	AD1599	5,06	-	-	-	Pl-Oliwa Kathedrale (Wazny pers comm.)
DUNTARVI	AD1385	AD1529	4,96	5,54	-	-	Duntarvi (Crone pers comm.)
8104M003	AD1357	AD1466	4,85	4,78	-	-	Understed K (Daly 1998a)
B012M001	AD1347	AD1484	4,25	5,36	-	-	Admiralgade (Daly 2005)
CD839Z01	AD1366	AD1511	4,23	5,08	-	-	Sulsted kirke (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007a)
8111M001	AD1350	AD1480	-	7,70	3,25	-	Astrup K. (Daly 1998b)
Shipwrecks from Scandinavia							
Z109M001	AD1437	AD1597	*	7,75	3,07	-	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo (Daly this report)
SNorway ships	AD1304	AD1895	10,77	7,43	-	-	SNorway ships 63 timber mean (Daly unpubl.)
Z0307M01	AD1435	AD1585	8,44	6,46	-	-	Barcode ship BC07 (Daly 2010c)
Z065M003	AD1355	AD1617	7,60	8,77	-	-	Bjørsvika Kenneth Oslo (Daly 2011c)
Z086M001	AD1468	AD1584	6,82	8,86	-	-	Havnelageret 1 boat (Daly 2012)
Z0306M01	AD1418	AD1585	5,66	7,57	-	-	Barcode 6 BC06 (Daly 2010a)
Z0302M01	AD1429	AD1587	5,64	6,18	-	-	Barcode BC02 (Daly 2010b)
LARVIK001	AD1480	AD1727	5,58	3,87	-	-	Larvik Ships 5 & 6 Norway (Daly 2007b)
Z0309M01	AD1395	AD1561	5,44	4,09	5,04	-	Barcode ship BC09 (Daly 2010d)
Z085m001	AD1397	AD1512	5,35	5,18	4,57	-	Barcode ship BC16 (Daly 2013a)
Z089m001	AD1399	AD1581	5,14	4,78	7,64	-	Barcode skib BC05 (Daly 2013b)
Z071m004	AD1304	AD1595	4,81	3,99	-	-	Barcode ship BC08 (Daly 2011d)
Z059m001	AD1371	AD1659	4,02	7,22	3,54	-	Klim Strandvraget (Daly 2011a)
00652M02	AD1405	AD1607	4,02	3,82	4,87	-	CPH B&W vrag 2 (Daly 2000b)
Z073m001	AD1385	AD1574	3,99	3,62	5,56	-	Barcode ship BC14 (Daly 2011d)
Z062m001	AD1384	AD1512	3,78	4,32	4,76	-	Oslo Vaterland I Schweigaardsgt 8 (Daly 2011b)
0207M001	AD1353	AD1410	\	6,24	-	\	Dokøen vrag 3 (Bonde & Eriksen 2002)
Z096M001	AD1378	AD1517	-	5,51	4,59	-	Bispevika 2 (Daly 2013d)

Table 2. Barcode ships BC01, BC03 & BC10, Oslo. Result of the correlation between tree-ring curves from all three ships and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Provenance

Table 1 shows the correlation between the tree-ring curves from each sample analysed here with each other. Tree-ring curves from six planks from BC01 (representing four trees) are averaged to form a mean curve Z109M001 of 161

years length. Similarly, the tree-ring curves from four planks from BC03 are averaged to Z110M001 of 260 years length.

In table 2 the correlation values (t-values) between the average tree-ring curves from ships BC01 and BC03 and the two individual tree-ring curves from the samples from BC10 and a selection of Northern European chronologies are shown.

BC01

The average tree-ring curve for BC01 matches best with data from other oak ships from the Oslo area, and with data from sites outside Norway known to include exported Norwegian oak. The ship was built of oaks from Southern Norway.

BC03

The average tree-ring curve for BC03 is also matching best with tree-ring data from other Norwegian ships from Oslo and exported Norwegian oak timber found at other sites. This ship was also built of oaks from Southern Norway.

BC10

While determining the provenance of single samples is difficult, it can be seen in table 2 that the two samples from BC10 are matching with quite separate regions. Sample x005 (Z111001a) is dating against other ship finds from Oslo, specifically with two of the Barcode ships, BC05 and BC14, both of which might come from western Sweden (Daly 2011c & 2013a). Sample x009 (Z111002a) in contrast is dating with data from the Southern Baltic region, specifically with data from painted oak panels, known through dendrochronology to be of Southern Baltic oak. If additional timbers from this ship are available, it is highly recommended that a more comprehensive analysis of this ship be undertaken, to address questions of the diverse origins of the timbers used in its construction.

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Catalogue

Catalogue format:

Filename
 Title and sample number
 Tree species (QUSP = *Quercus sp.*, oak, PISY = *Pinus sp.*, pine, PCAB = *Picea abies*, spruce) and number of years measured
 Chronological position of the tree-ring curve
 Number of sapwood years, presence of bark
 Felling date
 The measurements start at the innermost preserved ring

BC01

Z109001a

Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo plank bånddel x093 prøve 408

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 151 years length

Dated AD1437 to AD1587

4 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 130.38 Sensitivity 0.15

Interpretation same tree Z109001a, Z1090029 & Z1090059, AD1598-1607

278	247	334	342	356	298	417	250	282	282
285	279	345	411	380	277	217	150	155	152
112	92	80	79	71	88	80	65	78	78
67	83	66	52	57	60	47	51	64	87
65	99	130	157	179	260	251	179	164	114
107	121	125	128	158	140	173	175	152	144
147	148	114	126	135	157	135	163	137	154
194	213	162	159	143	167	157	101	106	129
108	95	82	95	105	114	104	105	135	133
144	117	141	158	134	137	118	93	100	86
77	88	106	75	78	104	89	83	65	71
74	88	62	66	86	95	67	72	75	70
43	73	74	73	79	84	81	101	78	100
81	67	96	91	85	82	98	109	89	92
115	97	100	85	80	72	90	90	75	80
71									

Z1090029

Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo plank bånddel x100 prøve 402

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 142 years length

Dated AD1456 to AD1597

11 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 103.43 Sensitivity 0.14

Interpretation same tree Z109001a, Z1090029 & Z1090059, AD1598-1607

73	75	69	60	75	67	82	69	70	65
86	82	101	83	79	101	103	76	90	92
129	81	121	132	122	148	223	215	192	187
103	105	113	109	128	120	109	128	117	107
96	108	104	88	108	127	123	107	114	131
117	148	168	140	117	129	136	145	113	101
119	98	94	79	87	99	111	94	101	122
107	130	111	129	194	148	153	143	112	111
103	84	86	114	101	100	120	109	98	84
79	78	86	78	78	99	94	81	84	85
79	64	83	79	84	88	84	78	109	80
94	85	71	100	93	82	77	83	102	94
124	117	99	102	91	103	95	95	86	98
96	94	105	80	86	70	93	81	88	87
75	123								

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Z109003a

Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo plank båddel x110 prøve 403

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 109 years length

Dated AD1481 to AD1589

6 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 149.86 Sensitivity 0.23

Interpretation AD1590-1604

119	156	122	121	199	155	173	160	190	231
159	78	167	109	135	142	93	104	76	79
180	218	145	136	174	182	221	228	218	171
190	189	218	154	198	189	204	284	163	109
163	142	125	150	220	218	227	178	217	184
158	173	134	87	84	148	97	114	165	91
102	119	127	107	127	107	143	173	115	113
117	119	130	134	185	171	152	193	178	181
220	326	187	304	208	231	218	126	202	151
179	104	115	99	140	133	182	87	79	74
80	79	51	66	75	58	58	48	48	

Z1090049

Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo plank båddel x120 prøve 404

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 139 years length

Dated AD1443 to AD1581

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 131.74 Sensitivity 0.21

Interpretation after AD1589

240	127	219	105	135	147	125	212	216	176
133	126	87	101	82	112	122	131	104	161
134	145	244	112	92	151	129	90	90	171
122	205	232	213	177	210	255	194	251	178
180	165	220	94	129	125	128	175	122	100
123	134	118	149	174	174	115	154	174	187
122	122	132	116	169	176	139	124	137	181
149	140	127	129	108	94	99	87	95	77
75	87	116	104	83	99	79	85	83	85
92	77	101	74	60	100	152	109	91	118
117	122	157	100	99	104	79	85	113	80
98	84	103	117	82	132	100	139	132	147
115	146	129	136	111	99	129	115	116	148
156	176	178	130	160	113	123	118	135	

Z1090059

Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo plank båddel x126 prøve 405

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 105 years length

Dated AD1475 to AD1579

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 99.59 Sensitivity 0.13

Interpretation same tree Z109001a, Z1090029 & Z1090059, AD1598-1607

93	123	94	110	124	118	140	169	165	139
126	89	96	102	114	118	113	113	125	116
96	96	105	93	79	95	99	98	82	95
103	104	141	157	141	118	104	122	115	91
92	104	92	85	73	73	86	93	77	89
115	103	120	88	114	161	112	112	125	90
93	80	67	83	93	87	91	101	83	90
78	82	86	104	73	70	102	90	76	82
80	83	60	75	67	75	77	78	71	86
80	92	79	71	106	87	91	83	98	112
112	116	114	104	124					

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Z109006a

Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo køl båddel x152 prøve 406

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 89 years length

Dated AD1503 to AD1591

8 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 117.94 Sensitivity 0.18

Interpretation AD1591-1604

95	101	90	75	93	66	72	83	63	65
42	58	57	60	41	40	42	70	119	121
72	48	57	55	75	73	119	91	80	105
157	114	115	112	71	74	203	190	157	169
151	195	184	177	141	140	101	99	131	127
118	115	123	132	131	146	159	132	144	164
162	168	160	133	135	123	146	142	107	92
120	171	169	153	130	86	106	89	107	116
167	241	197	154	120	151	163	125	164	

Z109007a

Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo repair plank båddel x160 prøve 407

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 108 years length

Dated AD1475 to AD1582

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 91.13 Sensitivity 0.18

Interpretation after AD1590

141	129	73	110	103	134	100	129	118	126
147	91	83	70	93	98	107	88	104	127
82	85	101	82	69	80	92	84	86	109
155	96	140	155	117	80	111	119	101	101
113	120	115	85	86	101	103	100	65	88
153	125	96	103	70	85	73	100	68	56
67	60	68	80	150	81	87	99	87	81
78	69	109	103	67	67	80	53	72	68
72	80	64	69	81	88	77	78	59	58
67	67	65	54	59	69	88	74	82	76
81	76	78	86	81	76	88	102		

BC03

Z110001a

Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo plank båddel x078 prøve 305

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 180 years length

Dated AD1406 to AD1585

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 133.22 Sensitivity 0.19

Interpretation after AD1593

253	279	265	288	266	250	255	269	228	97
168	210	236	261	266	251	239	152	126	72
73	94	107	110	99	112	150	105	153	108
123	151	137	96	98	92	91	124	125	123
116	127	137	151	172	168	166	135	146	155
96	65	105	121	160	124	141	91	129	153
97	124	87	86	127	146	164	115	114	100
112	64	101	81	130	145	209	128	107	123
95	110	100	113	104	91	95	98	101	92
109	108	88	82	93	135	103	93	82	91
93	116	122	106	101	165	142	137	114	96
121	134	157	86	97	141	115	107	137	153
144	132	115	144	189	148	83	100	76	130
91	159	145	149	109	158	171	201	156	143
83	111	121	93	110	147	146	140	126	114
134	133	141	114	158	192	149	150	145	149
144	148	131	189	172	120	113	72	75	110
162	140	105	113	91	134	131	80	114	93

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Z110002a

Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo plank båddel x085 prøve 306

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 260 years length

Dated AD1342 to AD1601

3 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 91.97 Sensitivity 0.17

Interpretation AD1605-19

136	162	133	127	80	77	50	62	91	124
111	103	83	99	119	86	107	119	124	151
145	108	129	123	141	158	138	102	99	79
72	108	117	97	122	102	74	90	102	150
165	206	338	224	266	228	105	81	85	85
72	79	78	89	72	106	114	96	141	209
148	168	157	154	138	131	129	126	115	105
99	86	88	58	60	56	59	78	59	76
90	71	86	75	65	59	58	61	73	82
89	73	94	71	125	102	137	199	150	123
151	156	97	102	96	118	122	119	145	162
135	121	105	80	98	71	84	94	94	96
113	87	94	108	99	82	93	65	92	108
132	101	128	99	93	62	80	76	84	86
83	73	89	88	89	79	74	78	87	98
90	99	103	102	96	88	103	78	63	76
83	76	84	96	115	119	122	106	99	107
99	85	81	58	77	67	80	61	65	95
85	67	73	82	88	75	90	72	90	75
72	66	64	93	72	51	73	80	56	77
73	86	81	62	75	58	70	68	60	80
66	68	66	56	58	52	74	86	78	84
80	60	75	66	68	69	59	56	47	66
66	53	47	49	47	50	41	59	41	35
44	42	40	54	64	60	47	56	55	49
53	39	56	44	43	53	51	49	70	55

Z110003a

Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo plank båddel x091 prøve 308

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 238 years length

Dated AD1356 to AD1593

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 98.43 Sensitivity 0.18

Interpretation after AD1601

202	212	223	228	202	183	175	240	176	133
140	162	107	188	167	177	120	134	164	103
95	83	60	95	94	76	123	161	246	140
141	131	69	74	74	69	70	106	93	94
85	85	140	132	133	127	105	112	140	183
146	125	115	135	119	97	113	122	113	84
69	149	113	100	99	108	170	118	112	116
93	99	103	115	107	114	143	97	144	89
89	112	75	144	117	79	140	178	116	140
131	150	126	126	109	171	124	125	76	80
71	72	91	122	115	95	112	105	85	108
80	85	74	84	105	115	97	82	104	84
90	49	69	90	89	103	127	84	63	105
65	80	90	86	107	90	69	99	81	74
62	80	77	71	62	84	95	82	82	81
90	102	97	105	84	93	111	80	74	69
83	85	84	83	71	78	83	78	86	103
100	87	74	66	100	73	65	59	58	63
62	43	56	82	68	64	57	72	60	51
68	56	62	65	55	71	68	62	70	61
61	53	69	77	78	69	56	69	77	67
76	75	80	101	92	83	78	73	49	56
80	81	73	51	54	51	69	79	80	91
85	76	61	89	68	62	64	57		

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Z110004a

Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo plank båddel x108 prøve 310

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 52 years length

Dated AD1554 to AD1605

8 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 219.94 Sensitivity 0.29

Interpretation AD1606-18

185	373	349	189	380	277	442	411	379	316
361	251	295	305	138	364	421	435	151	310
193	150	249	255	184	207	120	179	145	214
144	212	215	141	135	114	80	80	109	109
198	190	213	190	147	128	162	118	130	149
111	134								

Z110005a

Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo plank båddel x124 prøve 312

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 239 years length

Dated AD1357 to AD1595

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 96.03 Sensitivity 0.19

Interpretation after AD1603

314	369	238	158	156	147	195	202	244	236
250	129	151	166	218	127	217	197	125	129
90	58	65	58	59	106	124	159	124	100
130	74	90	82	83	67	102	98	74	113
92	110	115	120	110	136	115	150	177	140
112	139	152	84	104	152	137	76	79	87
115	85	85	80	114	141	112	74	66	75
85	84	67	74	87	122	67	77	52	68
93	68	45	56	55	57	79	70	77	85
86	79	82	106	91	92	99	91	58	47
51	54	75	87	82	97	89	82	99	78
59	66	54	96	99	150	118	121	160	140
71	86	99	121	143	187	118	97	125	72
93	90	90	140	116	103	127	130	96	105
104	119	79	98	137	113	106	104	92	98
109	123	103	82	106	121	114	93	72	97
79	82	74	61	70	70	72	88	71	79
85	56	64	81	60	60	52	52	70	63
54	76	95	76	84	60	75	65	68	61
52	78	56	66	77	67	62	71	54	59
58	74	79	76	79	69	87	81	67	80
79	68	78	68	75	74	60	47	65	68
73	69	74	41	59	62	55	82	77	84
69	51	68	51	47	51	47	65	56	

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BC10

Z111001a

Barcode ship 10 BC10 Oslo bånddel x005 prøve 031

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 191 years length

Dated AD1357 to AD1547

4 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 80.41 Sensitivity 0.27

Interpretation AD1550-64

119	116	181	245	143	42	45	24	24	24
102	126	237	190	52	38	40	39	25	22
25	16	21	46	91	117	85	183	147	104
226	108	48	48	36	41	95	74	96	73
76	89	143	145	145	119	128	115	128	92
129	143	94	99	71	88	83	69	31	43
47	43	32	38	44	52	35	58	44	47
66	67	47	56	48	77	50	91	56	67
47	52	26	42	37	44	83	53	60	43
54	36	43	43	53	59	58	50	45	34
27	32	27	33	36	31	47	45	61	45
47	54	53	35	30	37	44	36	43	57
63	51	40	36	53	68	65	75	72	63
99	78	45	51	55	68	89	68	71	60
82	59	40	51	62	76	84	121	179	100
230	214	194	221	213	156	137	78	123	158
115	98	64	45	59	88	71	89	78	150
131	116	85	83	124	190	119	89	68	61
74	75	144	109	118	180	146	104	104	76
66									

Z111002a

Barcode ship 10 BC10 Oslo bånddel x009 prøve 032

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 147 years length

Dated AD1387 to AD1533

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 136.53 Sensitivity 0.21

Interpretation after AD1543

303	224	188	204	207	305	185	203	201	237
167	206	158	130	127	159	137	164	157	174
93	90	92	94	124	98	158	215	152	192
130	175	140	196	231	211	190	112	181	154
190	261	133	79	111	208	155	142	108	126
131	136	107	167	159	164	290	192	211	158
129	170	148	144	145	122	109	149	89	152
104	99	78	68	51	49	46	43	43	47
48	49	43	37	47	37	41	41	51	69
78	65	81	98	162	124	131	102	101	125
140	114	120	100	88	82	73	62	78	70
64	77	85	76	93	116	107	127	95	136
160	170	183	196	158	153	161	209	314	193
176	175	149	178	294	173	164	148	122	228
166	119	94	82	115	103	177			

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	Conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	extra start	extra end	Interpretation / felling
	BC01										
Z109001a	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo plank bddel x093 prve 408 QUSP	151	AD1437	AD1587	T	F	4	-	-	-	AD1598-1607
Z1090029	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo plank bddel x100 prve 402QUSP	142	AD1456	AD1597	T	G	11	-	-	S1	AD1598-1607
Z109003a	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo plank bddel x110 prve 403 QUSP	109	AD1481	AD1589	T	G	6	-	-	S1	AD1590-1604
Z1090049	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo plank bddel x120 prve 404 QUSP	139	AD1443	AD1581	T	C	-	-	-	H1	after AD1589
Z1090059	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo plank bddel x126 prve 405 QUSP	105	AD1475	AD1579	T	G	-	-	-	H1	AD1598-1607
Z109006a	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo kl bddel x152 prve 406 QUSP	89	AD1503	AD1591	O	C	8	-	-	-	AD1591-1604
Z109007a	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo repair plank bddel x160 prve 407 QUSP	108	AD1475	AD1582	T	G	-	-	-	H1	after AD1590
Z109001_2_5 sametree	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo same tree 1 2 5 QUSP	161	AD1437	AD1597	T	F	11	-	-	S1	AD1598-1607
Z109M001	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo 4 timber mean QUSP	161	AD1437	AD1597							
	BC03										
Z110001a	Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo plank bddel x078 prve 305 QUSP	180	AD1406	AD1585	R	G	-	-	-	H1	after AD1593
Z110002a	Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo plank bddel x085 prve 306 QUSP	260	AD1342	AD1601	R	G	3	-	-	S1	AD1605-19
Z110003a	Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo plank bddel x091 prve 308 QUSP	238	AD1356	AD1593	T	G	-	-	-	H1	after AD1601
Z110004a	Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo plank bddel x108 prve 310 QUSP	52	AD1554	AD1605	T	G	8	-	-	S1	AD1606-18
Z110005a	Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo plank bddel x124 prve 312 QUSP	239	AD1357	AD1595	R	G	-	-	-	H1	after AD1603
Z110M001	Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo 4 timber mean QUSP	260	AD1342	AD1601							
	BC10										
Z111001a	Barcode ship 10 BC10 Oslo bddel x005 prve 031 QUSP	191	AD1357	AD1547	O	C	4	-	-	S1	AD1550-64
Z111002a	Barcode ship 10 BC10 Oslo bddel x009 prve 032 QUSP	147	AD1387	AD1533	O	G	-	-	-	H1	after AD1543
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.			26 November 2013								